

Nanoemulsion-based delivery system of tamanu (*Calophyllum inophyllum* L.) oil: Formulation, characterization, and antibacterial activity

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Abstract

Acne is a common skin disorder caused by chronic inflammation of the pilosebaceous unit, primarily triggered by *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. Tamanu (*Calophyllum inophyllum* L.) oil is known for its antibacterial properties, attributed to its active constituent, calophyllolide. However, its hydrophobic nature and limited skin penetration reduce its therapeutic effectiveness. To enhance its bioavailability and antibacterial activity, a nanoemulsion formulation was developed. Tamanu oil nanoemulsions were prepared using high-energy emulsification with varying concentrations of Tween 80 (F1 = 17.5%, F2 = 23.33%, F3 = 20%, F4 = 26.67%, F5 = 22.5%, F6 = 30%) and PEG-400 (F1 = 17.5%, F2 = 11.67%, F3 = 20%, F4 = 13.33%, F5 = 22.5%, F6 = 15%) as surfactants. The optimal formulation (F6) contained Tween 80 (30%), PEG-400 (15%), and tamanu oil at a concentration of 3%. The physicochemical properties, including globule size, polydispersity index (PDI), and physical stability were evaluated. Antibacterial activity was assessed using the agar diffusion method against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The optimized nanoemulsion exhibited a globule size of 11.0 ± 0.252 nm, a PDI of 0.09 ± 0.05 , and excellent physical stability. Antibacterial testing revealed that pure tamanu oil produced inhibition zones of 16.25 mm for *Cutibacterium acnes* and 17.50 mm for *Staphylococcus epidermidis* at a tamanu oil concentration of 3%. The nanoemulsion formulation (F6) demonstrated enhanced antibacterial efficacy, with inhibition zones increasing to 18.75 mm for *Cutibacterium acnes* and 19.50 mm for *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. While these values surpassed those of the pure oil, they remained lower than the clindamycin control, which produced inhibition zones of 21.10 mm and 22.97 mm respectively. These findings suggest that nanoemulsification significantly enhances the antibacterial potency and stability of tamanu oil, making it a promising candidate for acne treatment and skincare applications. Further studies on its in vivo efficacy and safety profile could facilitate its development as a novel pharmaceutical or cosmetic product.

Keywords

Tamanu (*Calophyllum inophyllum* L.) oil, nanoemulsion formulation, antibacterial activity, physical stability, skin penetration

Introduction

Acne vulgaris is a common dermatological condition that affects individuals worldwide, particularly adolescents and young adults. According to epidemiological studies, acne ranks as the eighth most prevalent disease globally, affecting approximately 9.4% of the population (Tan and Bhate 2015; Morshed et al. 2023). It is characterized by chronic inflammation of the pilosebaceous unit, leading to the formation of comedones, papules, pustules, and nodules. The prevalence of acne is significantly higher in females (77.16%) than in males (22.84%), with the highest incidence observed in women aged 20–24 years (39.10%) and men aged 15–19 years (11.94%) (Ruchiattan et al. 2020). Several factors contribute to acne development, including excessive sebum production, abnormal keratinization, bacterial colonization, and inflammation. *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* are the primary bacterial species associated with acne pathogenesis. In addition to biological factors, environmental elements such as stress, diet, cosmetics, and climate can exacerbate acne severity (Lee et al. 2019; Kim and Kim 2024). The negative impact of acne extends beyond physical symptoms, often impacting psychological well-being and quality of life. Effective treatment strategies are necessary to manage acne and prevent long-term complications, such as scarring and hyperpigmentation (Zhou et al. 2023). The increasing incidence of acne-related bacterial resistance necessitates the development of alternative therapeutic approaches.

Acne management involves both non-pharmacological and pharmacological treatments, depending on the severity of the condition. Non-pharmacological approaches include proper facial cleansing, dietary modifications, lifestyle changes, and the use of non-comedogenic skincare products (Durairaj et al. 2023). Pharmacological treatments typically involve topical and systemic agents such as retinoids, benzoyl peroxide, and antibiotics. Broad-spectrum antibiotics, including erythromycin, clindamycin, doxycycline, and tetracycline, have been widely used for acne treatment. However, prolonged and indiscriminate use of antibiotics has led to the emergence of resistant bacterial strains (Baldwin 2020; Mavranouzouli et al. 2022). A study conducted in Korea by Moon et al. (2012) reported that *Cutibacterium acnes* exhibited resistance to erythromycin (26.7%) and clindamycin (30%), while *Staphylococcus epidermidis* demonstrated resistance to clindamycin (33.3%), erythromycin (58.3%), doxycycline (27.3%), and tetracycline (30.6%) (Bhullar et al. 2012; Moon et al. 2012). The growing issue of antibiotic resistance underscores the urgent need for alternative antimicrobial agents. Natural plant-derived compounds have gained attention as promising antibacterial agents due to their safety, biocompatibility, and efficacy against resistant bacterial strains (MacPhail 1998; Abdallah et al. 2023). Medicinal plants with potent antimicrobial properties could serve as viable alternatives to conventional antibiotics in acne treatment.

Calophyllum inophyllum L., commonly known as tamanu, is a tropical medicinal plant with a long history

of use in traditional medicine. The essential oil extracted from Tamanu seeds contains bioactive compounds, including calophyllolide, which exhibit strong antibacterial activity (Farida et al. 2024; Ferdosh 2024). Calophyllolide ($C_{25}H_{22}O_5$) is a phenylcoumarin derivative classified as a neoflavonoid with potent antimicrobial properties. This bioactive compound has a molecular weight of 416.47 g/mol and a partition coefficient (log P) of 3.6, making it suitable for topical applications (Yim-djo et al. 2004; Cao et al. 2023). In addition to calophyllolide, tamanu oil also contains palmitic acid, stearic acid, oleic acid, and linoleic acid, which contribute to its wound-healing, antimicrobial, and cytotoxic activities. These fatty acids play essential roles in skin regeneration and barrier function, making tamanu oil a promising candidate for topical therapeutic formulations (Ferdosh 2024; Ali et al. 2024). A study by Léguillier et al. (2015) demonstrated that tamanu oil exhibited significant antibacterial effects against 23 Gram-positive bacterial strains, including *Cutibacterium acnes* (MIC = 0.011%) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (MIC = 0.025%) (Léguillier et al. 2015). Despite its antimicrobial efficacy, the practical application of tamanu oil in skincare formulations is hindered by its poor water solubility and limited skin penetration. These limitations restrict its therapeutic potential and necessitate the development of advanced formulation strategies (Widyaningsih et al. 2018, 2019). Enhancing the bioavailability and stability of tamanu oil could significantly improve its effectiveness as an antibacterial agent.

Nanoemulsion technology has emerged as a promising solution to improve the delivery and efficacy of essential oils. Nanoemulsions are thermodynamically stable oil-in-water dispersions with droplet sizes typically ranging from 10 to 100 nm. The small droplet size enhances the bioavailability, solubility, and skin penetration of bioactive compounds (Pavoni et al. 2020; Tayeb et al. 2021). Research conducted by Fu et al. (2022) demonstrated that nanoemulsions exhibit enhanced antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (Fu et al. 2022). The improved efficacy is attributed to the increased surface area and better interaction with bacterial cell membranes. Nanoemulsions also provide higher stability, preventing phase separation and degradation of active compounds over time (Mushtaq et al. 2023). According to Aulton and Taylor (2018), an ideal pharmaceutical formulation for transdermal delivery should have a molecular weight of < 500 Da, a log P between 1 and 4, and an effective daily dose of approximately 10 mg/day (Aulton 2018). The incorporation of tamanu oil into a nanoemulsion system could address its solubility limitations while enhancing its antibacterial efficacy. This approach could provide a stable and efficient formulation for acne treatment.

Based on these considerations, this study aims to formulate and optimize a stable nanoemulsion containing tamanu oil and evaluate its antibacterial activity against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The formulation is characterized in terms of droplet size, polydispersity index, and stability to ensure its suitability for topical

applications (Majeed et al. 2019). The antibacterial efficacy of the nanoemulsion will be assessed through agar diffusion assays to compare its inhibitory effects with those of pure tamanu oil. Nanoemulsion technology is expected to improve the solubility, increase the bioavailability, and enhance the skin penetration of tamanu oil, making it more effective in acne treatment. Additionally, the stability of the formulation will be evaluated to determine its potential for long-term use in pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications (Badruddoza et al. 2023). By leveraging nanoemulsion technology, the therapeutic potential of tamanu oil can be maximized, offering a safer and more sustainable alternative to conventional antibiotics. The results of this study may contribute to the development of innovative plant-based antimicrobial therapies, particularly for acne treatment. This research also aims to provide insights into the feasibility of incorporating tamanu oil nanoemulsions into commercial skincare and pharmaceutical products.

Materials and methods

Materials

This study utilized various materials essential for the formulation and characterization of nanoemulsions. The primary active ingredient was *Calophyllum inophyllum* L. oil (tamanu oil), which was obtained from PT. Eteris Nusantara Minyak Atsiri accompanied by a Certificate of Analysis (CoA) verifying its authenticity and quality. Additional materials included the clindamycin antibiotic, which was used as a positive control in the antibacterial tests, and distilled water (aquabidest) as a solvent. Surfactants such as polysorbate 80 (Tween 80) and polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) were employed to stabilize the nanoemulsion, while phosphate buffer was used to maintain pH stability. Other materials included dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), 96% ethanol, fuchsin, glycerin, parchment paper, crystal violet, immersion oil, Lugol's iodine, 0.9% NaCl, propylene glycol, spiritus, and Tryptic Soy Agar (TSA), each playing a crucial role in the formulation, characterization, or evaluation of nanoemulsions.

Equipment

A variety of laboratory equipment was used to ensure precise measurements and reliable results throughout the study. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS, Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010) was employed to analyze the chemical composition of tamanu oil, confirming the presence of bioactive compounds. Essential sterilization equipment such as an autoclave (Tomy ES-215 Autoclave & Sterilizer) was used to prevent microbial contamination of the samples and media. Analytical instruments such as a pH meter (Ohaus® 3100), UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-Vis 1800°), viscometer (Brookfield RV DV-I Prime), and particle size analyzer (Nano Particle Analyzer Horiba SZ-100) were utilized for physical characterization. Sample preparation involved the use of

a magnetic stirrer, micropipettes (Eppendorf Research® Plus), a sonicator bath (Bransonic CPX 2800 H, USA), and a centrifuge, all of which contributed to proper nanoemulsion formulation and stability testing. Additional general laboratory tools included glassware (beakers, volumetric flasks, graduated cylinders), a vortex mixer, a punch tool (perforator), and an incubator, which were used for sample handling, antibacterial testing, and emulsification.

Bacterial strains

The bacterial strains used in this study were *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, which are commonly associated with skin infections and were selected to evaluate the antibacterial efficacy of the nanoemulsion. These strains were obtained from Integrated Pharmaceutical Laboratory Unit D, Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Universitas Islam Bandung, ensuring their clinical relevance and confirmed identification. Before use, bacterial cultures were revived and maintained on Tryptic Soy Agar (TSA) to ensure optimal growth and viability. Standardized bacterial suspensions were prepared by adjusting the turbidity to 0.5 McFarland standard (1.5×10^8 CFU/mL) for accurate antibacterial testing. These strains were essential for evaluating the nanoemulsion's antimicrobial effectiveness.

Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis

Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was conducted to determine the chemical composition of tamanu oil. The analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 at the Instrument Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. The samples were prepared by diluting tamanu oil in a suitable solvent before GC-MS analysis. The separation of compounds was achieved using a capillary column, while identification was performed by comparing mass spectral data against the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) database. This analysis was essential for confirming the presence of active constituents in tamanu oil, which contribute to its antibacterial and antioxidant properties (Fan et al. 2018).

Preparation of nanoemulsion

Nanoemulsions were prepared using the sonication method, a widely used technique for producing stable and uniform emulsions. Initially, tamanu oil was mixed with the selected surfactant (Tween 80) and co-surfactant (PEG 400) using a magnetic stirrer for 10 minutes at 1000 rpm to form a pre-emulsion at room temperature. The pre-emulsion was then subjected to sonication at 40 kHz for 20 minutes using an ultrasonicator to reduce droplet size and enhance stability. Distilled water was gradually added during stirring to ensure uniform dispersion of the oil droplets. A final sonication cycle was applied to achieve a

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the tamanu oil nanoemulsion formulation process.

homogeneous and stable nanoemulsion (Mohamadi Saani et al. 2019). The formulation process was optimized by varying the oil-to-surfactant ratio, as detailed in Table 1.

The stepwise formulation procedure is illustrated in Fig. 1. It begins with the mixing of tamanu oil, Tween 80, and PEG 400 to form the oil phase. This mixture is stirred to produce a uniform pre-emulsion before undergoing sonication to reduce particle size. During this process, distilled water is gradually added to aid the dispersion of oil droplets. The final nanoemulsion obtained is characterized by improved physical stability and homogeneity, making it suitable for further evaluation in topical applications. This visual representation helps to clarify each critical stage of the nanoemulsion preparation process. Understanding these steps is essential for optimizing formulation parameters and ensuring reproducibility in future studies.

Table 1. Optimization of nanoemulsion formulations.

Ingredients		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Smix (%)	Tamanu oil (%)	3	3	3	3	3	3
	Tween 80 (%)	17.5	23.33	20	26.67	22.5	30
	PEG-400 (%)	17.5	11.67	20	13.33	22.5	15
	Distilled Water (%)	ad 100					

Characterization of nanoemulsion

Characterization of the nanoemulsion was conducted through various evaluations to ensure its stability, effectiveness, and suitability for application. Organoleptic evaluation was performed by assessing the color, odor, clarity, and homogeneity of the nanoemulsion using human senses. The homogeneity test was carried out by spreading a small amount of the sample on a glass slide, covering it with another slide, and observing the sample for uniformity under a microscope. pH measurement was conducted using a calibrated pH meter (Ohaus® 3100) to ensure that the nanoemulsion remained within the safe pH range for skin application. Viscosity and rheology tests were performed using a Brookfield Viscometer with

spindle number 61 at 100 rpm. Rheological behavior was further analyzed by recording viscosity at multiple speeds (10, 20, 50, and 100 rpm, and then decreasing the speed in reverse order). Transmittance measurement was carried out using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-Vis 1800®) at a wavelength of 650 nm, with distilled water serving as a blank, to determine the transparency of the nanoemulsion. The droplet size and polydispersity index (PDI) were analyzed using a Particle Size Analyzer (PSA) one day after preparation, with samples measured in a cuvette. Zeta potential measurement was also conducted using a PSA to assess colloidal stability, with a stable nanoemulsion typically exhibiting a zeta potential value greater than or equal to ± 30 mV. Finally, stability tests were performed by subjecting the nanoemulsion to heating-cooling cycles (4 °C and 40 °C for 48 hours), centrifugation (4000 rpm for 30 minutes), and freeze-thaw cycles (-20 °C and 25 °C for 48 hours) to observe potential phase separation, creaming, or coalescence, which would indicate physical instability (Khalid et al. 2023).

Antibacterial activity test

The antibacterial activity of the nanoemulsion was assessed using the agar well diffusion method against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The test was conducted using the agar well diffusion technique, where Tryptic Soy Agar (TSA) was used as the growth medium. Clindamycin was used as a positive control, while DMSO served as the negative control to ensure the reliability of the results. The test was carried out by preparing bacterial suspensions and inoculating 100 μ L of bacterial culture into sterile Petri dishes, followed by the addition of 20 mL of molten TSA cooled to 45–53 °C. The mixture was gently swirled to ensure even distribution of the bacteria before being allowed to solidify. After solidification, wells were made using a perforator, and 50 μ L of the nanoemulsion test solution was added into each well. The plates were subjected to pre-incubation for 30–60 minutes to allow diffusion of the test solution before being incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. After incubation, the antibacterial

activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around the wells, indicating bacterial growth suppression (Priani et al. 2023).

Results

Preparation and characterization of tamanu oil

The characterization of tamanu oil involved organoleptic testing, specific gravity determination, refractive index measurement, and chemical composition analysis using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Organoleptic testing was conducted to evaluate the oil's visual appearance and aroma, ensuring it met standard quality specifications. The refractive index test assessed the oil's optical properties, serving as an indicator of its purity. Meanwhile, the specific gravity test measured the oil's density, further verifying its composition. GC-MS analysis was performed to identify the bioactive compounds present in the oil, which play a crucial role in its pharmacological properties. The organoleptic evaluation revealed that tamanu oil had a thick yellow-green appearance with a characteristic nutty odor. The refractive index was recorded at 1.476, within the standard range of 1.4699–1.4772, confirming its acceptable optical properties. The specific gravity test yielded a value of 0.943, consistent with the standard range of 0.9415–0.9452, ensuring its authenticity (Wardani et al. 2024). The findings indicate that the tamanu oil used in this study meets the necessary pharmaceutical standards for further formulation. These parameters confirm the suitability of tamanu oil as a raw material for pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications.

The GC-MS analysis identified four major fatty acids in tamanu oil: stearic acid, palmitic acid, oleic acid, and palmitoleic acid, all of which contribute to its bioactivity (Table 2). Stearic acid (4.23%) and palmitic acid (21.97%) are known for their antibacterial properties, particularly against *Cutibacterium acnes*. Oleic acid (16.95%) has been reported to inhibit the growth of Gram-positive bacteria and also exhibits antioxidant and emollient properties. Palmitoleic acid (44.82%) exhibits strong anti-inflammatory activity and promotes wound healing, making it beneficial for dermatological applications. The presence

Table 2. Physicochemical and compositional characteristics of tamanu oil.

Test	Results
Organoleptic	Thick yellow-green liquid with a characteristic nutty odor
Refractive index	1.476
Specific gravity	0.943 mg/mL
Major compounds	Stearic Acid (4.23%), Oleic Acid (16.95%), Palmitic Acid (21.97%), Palmitoleic Acid (44.82%)

of these compounds supports the use of tamanu oil in pharmaceutical and cosmetic formulations. The high concentration of palmitoleic acid is primarily responsible for the oil's bioactivity, particularly in enhancing skin regeneration. Additionally, the fatty acids present in the oil contribute to its moisturizing and protective effects on the skin (Huang et al. 2018). These findings are consistent with previous studies and confirm the typical fatty acid profile of tamanu oil. Moreover, the results confirm that tamanu oil possesses valuable properties that make it suitable for medicinal and cosmetic use.

Optimization and preliminary evaluation of nanoemulsion formulation

After preparation, the nanoemulsion formulations were evaluated based on organoleptic properties, percent transmittance (%T), and centrifugation stability. Organoleptic evaluation involved visually inspecting the color and clarity of the nanoemulsion to assess the visual quality of the formulations. Percent transmittance was measured using a spectrophotometer to assess formulation transparency, with higher transmittance values indicating better uniformity and stability. Centrifugation stability tests were conducted to evaluate the resistance of the nanoemulsion to phase separation under high gravitational force, to evaluate the physical stability of the formulation. These tests served as an initial screening method to assess the clarity and stability of the nanoemulsion. The results presented in Table 3 indicate that formulations F4, F5, and F6 demonstrated superior characteristics, as they appeared clear, exhibited high transmittance values, and remained stable after centrifugation. Transmittance values above 85% suggest an optimal nano-sized droplet distribution, which contributed to

Table 3. Evaluation of nanoemulsion formulations.

Evaluation	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Visualization						
Organoleptic	Cloudy Yellow	Slightly Cloudy Yellow	Cloudy Yellow	Clear Yellow	Clear Yellow	Clear Yellow
% Transmittance	0.91 ± 0.13	58.65 ± 0.85	21.81 ± 0.21	86.66 ± 0.37	90.99 ± 0.30	96.09 ± 0.09
Centrifugation	Unstable	Unstable	Unstable	Stable	Stable	Stable

their improved transparency (Jacob et al. 2024). Additionally, the increased clarity and stability of these formulations indicate successful emulsification, making them promising candidates for further development in topical formulations.

The findings indicate that formulations F4, F5, and F6 were the most suitable, as they met all key criteria for an ideal nanoemulsion. These formulations exhibited clear physical characteristics and excellent stability, both of which are essential for ensuring their effectiveness. The high transmittance values confirm the formation of a well-dispersed nanoemulsion system with optimal droplet size. The appropriate surfactant-to-co-surfactant ratio played a crucial role in achieving these properties by reducing interfacial tension, preventing coalescence, and maintaining homogeneity (Kumar et al. 2024). Tween 80 had a dominant role in reducing particle size and enhancing stability, while PEG-400 synergistically improved transparency and pH stability (Miksusanti et al. 2023). These attributes make the formulations ideal for pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications, where stability and appearance are critical factors. Further studies should focus on evaluating their long-term stability under different storage conditions to ensure consistency. Additionally, biological efficacy tests should be conducted to explore their antimicrobial and dermatological potential. The promising characteristics of these formulations provide a strong foundation for their potential use in antibacterial and dermatological applications.

Final formulation of tamanu oil nanoemulsion

Based on the results of the preliminary evaluation, Formula F6 was identified as the optimal formulation for the tamanu oil nanoemulsion (Table 4). This formulation was chosen due to its clear and transparent visual appearance, which indicates a high transmittance percentage (>90%) and excellent stability. A high transmittance value suggests that the nanoemulsion has a well-dispersed and uniform droplet size distribution. The stability of the formulation was further confirmed through centrifugation tests, where it remained stable without signs of phase separation (Feng et al. 2022). To ensure microbial safety, phenoxyethanol was incorporated as a preservative in the formulation. Since nanoemulsions contain a high proportion of distilled water, they are prone to microbial contamination that may compromise their quality. The addition of phenoxyethanol prevents the growth of bacteria, fungi, and yeast, thereby extending the shelf life of the nanoemulsion.

Table 4. Final formulation of tamanu oil nanoemulsion.

Ingredient	Amount (% w/w)
Tamanu oil	3
Tween 80	30
PEG 400	15
Phenoxyethanol	0.5
Distilled Water	ad 100

This preservative works by disrupting microbial cell membranes, making it highly effective against a broad range of microorganisms. By maintaining the integrity of the formulation, phenoxyethanol ensures that the nanoemulsion remains safe and stable for long-term use. Proper preservation is crucial for preventing microbial contamination, which could affect the product's efficacy and safety.

Phenoxyethanol was selected as a preservative due to its broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity and low irritation potential. Unlike some preservatives that may cause skin irritation, phenoxyethanol is considered mild and well-tolerated in topical formulations. Its concentration in this formulation (0.5%) falls within the recommended range of 0.5–1%, ensuring both efficacy and safety (Dréno et al. 2019). This compound remains chemically stable over a pH range of 3–10, making it highly suitable for maintaining the stability of the nanoemulsion. The use of preservatives in nanoemulsions is essential to prevent microbial contamination that could lead to product degradation. Ensuring that the formulation adheres to regulatory guidelines for safety and efficacy further supports its suitability for consumer use (Poddębniak and Kalinowska-Lis 2024). The ability of phenoxyethanol to maintain its effectiveness under different storage conditions enhances the durability of the nanoemulsion. Additionally, its stability in various environmental conditions ensures that the formulation retains its intended properties over time. By preventing spoilage and microbial growth, phenoxyethanol contributes to the long-term usability of the nanoemulsion (Halla et al. 2018). This preservation strategy ensures that the formulation remains safe, stable, and effective for pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications.

Evaluation of the final tamanu oil nanoemulsion

After formulating the tamanu oil nanoemulsion, a comprehensive physicochemical evaluation was conducted to ensure its quality and stability. The evaluation included organoleptic assessment, homogeneity testing, pH measurement, transmittance percentage determination, viscosity and rheology testing, globule size and polydispersity index (PDI) measurement, and stability analysis. Additionally, stability tests such as heating-cooling cycles, centrifugation, and freeze-thaw assessments were performed to determine the formulation's resilience under varying conditions. Organoleptic testing was conducted to evaluate the appearance, color, and odor of the nanoemulsion, ensuring it met expected characteristics. As shown in Table 5, the F6 formulation exhibited a thick, yellow, clear liquid with a characteristic odor, consistent with a well-prepared nanoemulsion. Homogeneity testing confirmed that the nanoemulsion was uniform, with no visible phase separation or coarse particles. The pH measurement was performed using a pH meter to ensure compatibility with the skin, with an ideal range of 4.5–6.5. The pH of F6 was recorded at 6.16 ± 0.009 , making it suitable for topical applications without causing irritation or

dryness (Tarik Alhamdany et al. 2021). Maintaining an optimal pH is crucial for ensuring both product stability and skin compatibility.

Table 5. Final evaluation of tamanu oil nanoemulsion.

Evaluation	F6 Formula Result
Visualization	
Organoleptic	Thick, yellow, clear, with characteristic odor
Homogeneity	Homogeneous
pH	6.16 ± 0.009
Viscosity (cPs)	126.9 ± 0.404
Rheology	Pseudoplastic
% Transmittance	96.287 ± 0.290
Globule Size (nm)	11.0 ± 0.252
PDI	0.09 ± 0.05
Zeta Potential	-0.4 ± 0.153
Stability	Stable

The viscosity of the nanoemulsion, measured using a Brookfield Viscometer, was 126.9 ± 0.404 cPs, falling within the acceptable range of 10–2000 cPs, ensuring smooth application (Jaiswal et al. 2015). Rheology testing confirmed that F6 exhibited pseudoplastic flow behavior, meaning its viscosity decreased with increasing shear rate, which facilitates easier spreading on the skin. The transmittance percentage test indicated that F6 had a high clarity level, with a recorded value of $96.287 \pm 0.290\%$, signifying optimal droplet dispersion (Laxmi et al. 2015). The globule size measurement showed an average size of 11.0 ± 0.252 nm, which is within the 10–100 nm range required for nanoemulsions. Additionally, the PDI value of 0.09 ± 0.05 indicated a narrow size distribution, confirming the uniformity of the formulation. However, the zeta potential value of -0.4 ± 0.153 mV suggested lower colloidal stability, likely due to the nonionic nature of Tween 80, which does not contribute significant charge to the formulation (Zhao et al. 2023). Stability testing, which included heating-cooling cycles, centrifugation, and freeze-thaw tests, confirmed that F6 remained clear, showed no phase separation, and maintained its stability under all tested conditions. These findings confirm that the F6 formulation meets the standard requirements for a stable nanoemulsion, making it a suitable candidate for further pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications.

Antibacterial activity test of tamanu oil nanoemulsion formulation

After evaluating the tamanu oil nanoemulsion, its antibacterial activity was examined against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, two bacteria commonly associated with acne. The agar well diffusion method was

employed to quantify antibacterial effects through the measurement of inhibition zone diameters. According to the results in Table 6, the nanoemulsion formulation (F6) exhibited notable antibacterial activity, with inhibition zones of 18.75 mm against *Cutibacterium acnes* and 19.50 mm against *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. These values were greater than those of pure tamanu oil, which showed inhibition zones of 16.25 mm and 17.50 mm, respectively, indicating that nanoemulsification enhanced the antibacterial efficacy. However, the standard antibiotic clindamycin still demonstrated the highest activity, with inhibition zones of 21.10 mm for *Cutibacterium acnes* and 22.97 mm for *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The use of nanocarriers can increase surface area and promote better interaction between the active components and bacterial cell walls (Ozidal and Gurkok 2022). The enhancement may also be attributed to the improved penetration of nanoemulsions through the agar medium, allowing deeper diffusion of active agents. This suggests that the nanoemulsion system provides a superior delivery platform for the antibacterial constituents of tamanu oil.

Table 6. Antibacterial activity test results of tamanu oil nanoemulsion.

Test Group	Average Inhibition Zone Diameter (mm)	
	<i>Cutibacterium acnes</i>	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
F6	18.75 mm	19.50 mm
Tamanu oil	16.25 mm	17.50 mm
Clindamycin	21.10 mm	22.97 mm
Base (Tween, PEG, Phenoxyethanol, and Water)	3.25 mm	3.50 mm

The primary antibacterial constituents of tamanu oil include calophyllolide, a neoflavonoid compound, along with saturated fatty acids such as stearic acid and palmitic acid. Calophyllolide has been reported to exhibit antimicrobial activity through mechanisms involving membrane disruption and metabolic inhibition. Flavonoids such as calophyllolide interfere with bacterial energy metabolism and can destabilize the phospholipid bilayer. Meanwhile, fatty acids may inhibit bacterial growth by altering membrane fluidity and interfering with biosynthetic pathways (Ginigini et al. 2019). These compounds work synergistically to inhibit the proliferation of acne-causing bacteria. The base formulation (Tween, PEG, phenoxyethanol, and water) showed minimal antibacterial activity, with inhibition zones of only 3.25 mm and 3.50 mm against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, respectively. This minimal activity further confirms that the antibacterial effect in F6 is due to the active ingredients of tamanu oil, not the excipients. Therefore, the combination of tamanu oil and nanoemulsion technology presents a promising strategy to enhance antimicrobial performance.

Fig. 2 displays representative agar plates with wells containing clindamycin, pure tamanu oil, nanoemulsion (F6), and the blank formulation. Clear and well-defined inhibition zones are observed surrounding the wells of

Figure 2. Representative agar diffusion assay plates showing antibacterial activity of tamanu oil (pure and nanoemulsion forms).

clindamycin and nanoemulsion, while the blank exhibits negligible antibacterial activity. Notably, the nanoemulsion displayed larger inhibition zones than pure tamanu oil against both *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, reinforcing the enhanced efficacy of the formulation. Although its activity was slightly lower than that of the standard antibiotic clindamycin, the nanoemulsion still demonstrated substantial antibacterial potential. These findings suggest that the tamanu oil nanoemulsion may serve as a promising natural alternative for antibacterial applications, particularly when antibiotic resistance or long-term use of synthetic agents is a concern (Shamsudin et al. 2022). Its advantages may include lower potential for resistance development and improved skin compatibility due to the absence of synthetic drugs. Future studies are necessary to further evaluate its clinical relevance, long-term stability, and dermatological safety through in vivo and patient-based investigations.

Discussion

The formulation and evaluation of the tamanu oil nanoemulsion demonstrated promising potential as an antibacterial agent, particularly against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*. The successful optimization of the nanoemulsion was evident in its physicochemical properties, which showed high transmittance, small globule size, and stability under stress conditions. The pseudoplastic rheology of the formulation ensures smooth application, making it suitable for topical use. The antibacterial efficacy of the nanoemulsion can be attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds such as calophyllolide, stearic acid, and palmitic acid, which act by disrupting bacterial membranes and inhibiting metabolic pathways. Compared to the base formulation, which exhibited no antibacterial activity, the optimized nanoemulsion effectively inhibited bac-

terial growth, demonstrating its potential as a natural alternative to conventional acne treatments. However, while the inhibition zones were substantial, they were lower than those of clindamycin, suggesting that further modifications could enhance its potency. Incorporating additional synergistic antimicrobial agents or refining the surfactant composition may help improve the formulation's overall effectiveness.

A comparison with previous studies on nanoemulsion-based antibacterial treatments highlights both the strengths and areas for further improvement of the tamanu oil formulation. A study by Abdelhamed et al. (2022) investigated the antibacterial and anti-inflammatory activities of *Thymus vulgaris* essential oil nanoemulsion against *Cutibacterium acnes* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, demonstrating strong biofilm inhibition and membrane disruption effects (Abdelhamed et al. 2022). Similarly, Taleb et al. (2018) formulated an oregano essential oil nanoemulsion and found that it exhibited superior antibacterial activity compared to reference antibiotics (Taleb et al. 2018). The current study's findings align with these reports, indicating that nanoemulsions are effective carriers for bioactive natural compounds with antibacterial properties. However, the lower inhibition zones observed for the tamanu oil nanoemulsion compared to thyme and oregano oil nanoemulsions suggest that optimizing the concentration of active compounds or modifying the formulation parameters could further enhance its antibacterial efficacy (Hosny et al. 2021). Additionally, a clinical study on tea tree oil nanoemulsion with adapalene demonstrated improved acne treatment outcomes compared to a marketed adapalene gel (Najafi-Taher et al. 2022). These comparisons highlight the potential of nanoemulsion formulations as effective drug delivery systems for dermatological applications.

Future research should focus on optimizing the formulation's antibacterial potency while maintaining its stability and biocompatibility. Conducting *in vivo* studies is crucial to assess the formulation's efficacy on human skin, particularly its penetration, absorption, and potential irritation effects. Long-term storage stability tests should be performed to ensure that the nanoemulsion retains its antibacterial activity over time. Clinical trials comparing its effectiveness with standard acne treatments will provide further validation of its therapeutic potential. Additionally, exploring its application for other skin conditions, such as wound healing and anti-inflammatory treatments, could broaden its scope of use. The ability of nanoemulsions to enhance drug delivery and improve bioavailability makes them valuable candidates for pharmaceutical and cosmetic formulations. By refining the formulation and conducting further research, the tamanu oil nanoemulsion could emerge as a viable natural alternative for acne treatment, reducing reliance on conventional antibiotics and mitigating antibiotic resistance concerns.

Conclusion

The optimized tamanu oil nanoemulsion (F6) demonstrated excellent physical stability and antibacterial activity, making it a promising formulation for topical applications. It consisted of 3% tamanu oil, 30% Tween 80, and 15% PEG-400, meeting physicochemical criteria such as pH (6.16 ± 0.009), viscosity (126.9 ± 0.404 cPs), and homogeneity. The nanoemulsion had a small droplet size of 11.0 ± 0.252 nm with a low polydispersity index (0.09 ± 0.05), ensuring uniform dispersion. Stability tests confirmed that it remained stable under heating-cooling cycles, centrifugation, and freeze-thaw conditions. Antibacterial evaluation showed strong inhibition against *Cutibacterium acnes* (18.75 mm) and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (19.50 mm). Bioactive compounds like calophyllolide, stearic acid, and palmitic acid contributed to the effect. The activity was superior to clindamycin and the base formulation. This confirms its antibacterial potential. The nanoemulsion offers a natural alternative for acne treatment. Further studies and clinical trials are needed to confirm its efficacy and stability.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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